

ACCESS-NRI AUSTRALIA'S CLIMATE SIMULATOR

WORK PLAN

2026-2027

The Australian Government enables ACCESS-NRI through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy, NCRIS.

We at ACCESS-NRI acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the land on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth systems we simulate.

Annual Work Plan

FY2026–2027

Executive Summary

The FY2026–27 Annual Work Plan outlines ACCESS-NRI’s priorities to strengthen Australia’s national climate modelling capability through the continued development, delivery and support of the ACCESS framework. The plan is informed by extensive community consultation and aligned with strategic goals, reflecting community priorities and current capacity.

Work is structured across four key areas: **model development and release, infrastructure, software and data**, and **training and engagement**. Key priorities include delivering new and updated ACCESS model configurations, improving the underlying infrastructure and workflows, enhancing data quality, discovery and reproducibility, advancing tools for evaluation and analysis, and improving software performance and portability.

A stronger focus on user experience is reflected in this year’s plan, with activities aimed at improving how users interact with ACCESS models, data and tools. This work is supported by enhanced documentation, targeted training and ongoing user support, informed by user feedback and consultation. The plan also includes continued support for Community Working Groups, workshops, communication and outreach activities, and the expanded ACCESS-NRI PhD Internship Program.

Overall, the work plan aims to deliver a more robust, accessible and integrated ACCESS ecosystem that supports high-impact climate science and informed decision-making.

Introduction

Australia's climate simulator, ACCESS-NRI, is Australia's national research infrastructure for climate modelling. Our role is to develop, maintain and support the Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator (ACCESS), and to enable its use by the broader research community for high-impact science and informed decision-making.

This Annual Work Plan outlines ACCESS-NRI's proposed priorities and activities for FY2026–27. The plan reflects continued focus on delivering and supporting ACCESS model releases, strengthening the software and data infrastructure that underpins climate modelling workflows, and supporting the tools and services used by the ACCESS community. It also includes an emphasis on user experience, community feedback and engagement, alongside continued support in training, documentation and user support.

The development of this work plan included multiple opportunities for community input and feedback. An initial stage of community input helped shape the draft work plan, while a second stage of feedback allowed refinements to the proposed activities and priorities. Overall, we received 85 suggestions between the two feedback stages. While not all proposed activities could be accommodated within current resourcing and capacity, many suggestions aligned strongly with existing multi-year activities and have been incorporated where possible. Final prioritisation considered alignment with strategic objectives, community needs and current funding.

Following development of this work plan, ACCESS-NRI was successful in securing additional funding through the 2025–26 NCRIS funding opportunity. Planning for this new work is still underway and activities associated with this funding are therefore not reflected in the current work plan.

Activities for this year are structured across four key areas:

1. Model development and release
2. Infrastructure
3. Software and data
4. Training and engagement

Many activities in this plan are delivered in partnership with universities, government agencies, NCRIS facilities and national research programs, alongside collaborations with international modelling and software communities.

How to read this work plan

Activities indicate multi-year areas of interest for ACCESS-NRI. For each activity, the description text outlines the key objectives, planned milestones and, where relevant, stretch goals for the year. The listed teams indicate the primary internal and external contributors involved in delivering the work, while the effort estimates provide an approximation of ACCESS-NRI resourcing required across the activity. These sections are intended to help our community understand both the planned outcomes and the scale and coordination needed to deliver them.

The ordering of the activities is not priority-based. The activities in the table are grouped by the lead team for the activity and then sorted alphabetically by lead team and activity name. Cross-organisation activities are listed at the end of the tables. Within an activity, the goals are listed in priority order as much as possible.

Work Plan

Model development and release

In 2026–27, ACCESS-NRI will continue to advance the ACCESS modelling framework through coordinated development and release activities across the atmosphere, ocean, land, sea ice, ice sheet and regional systems (Table 1). Our focus remains on delivering robust, reproducible model configurations that support a wide range of scientific applications.

Planned work includes new releases across ACCESS model components and configurations as well as evaluation work of various ACCESS models. Goals for this year include the release of ACCESS-ESM1.6 configurations and experiments, beta releases of ACCESS-CM3 and ACCESS-rAM3 with CABLE for the land surface model, a release of a “whole of Antarctic” ice-sheet configuration, ACCESS-AIS3, alpha releases of ACCESS-OM3-8km and ACCESS-OM3-100km with WaveWatchIII, and alpha releases of the PanAntarctic configurations with and without ice shelves.

For more information on our various release stages, please see our [release documentation](#).

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 2, 3 and 4

Table 1: Model development and release activities for FY2026–27

Activity	Description	Team(s)*	Effort**
ACCESS coupled model	<p>Release of all DECK experiments for ACCESS-ESM1.6 and contributions to ESM1.6 release documentation and paper. Alpha and beta release of ACCESS-CM3 with CABLE3, including a Spack build, automated testing and continued evaluation coordination, running of the model evaluation and collection of analysis notebooks. Also includes shared datasets from control experiments. Alpha release of ACCESS-ESM3.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Release of additional CMIP7 and ESM1.6 community configurations (encourage transition from ESM1.5).</i> • <i>Setup and test potentially faster configurations, e.g. N48 ESM1.6, UKESMfast-like CM3. Survey community on requirements.</i> • <i>Support the community to develop a framework for idealised simulations</i> • <i>Test coupling of higher than standard resolution components.</i> 	<p>Atmosphere, Ocean, Model Release, Land</p> <p><i>Collaborators: CSIRO, BoM</i></p>	1.65
Ancillary suites and tools	<p>Create workflows for atmosphere and land ancillary files for ACCESS models. This includes ACCESS-ESM1.6 ancillaries for CMIP7 beyond Fast Track, ACCESS-ESM3 ancillaries for CMIP7 and high-resolution ACCESS-CM3 and AM3 ancillaries for HighResMIP. Release the ancillary suite for generation 3 ACCESS models with CABLE, for all supported science configurations.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Trialling an ancillary and restart validation tool</i> 	<p>Atmosphere, Land</p> <p><i>Collaborators: 21st Century Weather</i></p>	0.45
ACCESS ice sheet model	<p>Development of pyISSM to reach ‘parity’ with core ISSM MATLAB interface functionality – moving from minor 0.x releases to full release including community support, training and workflow development. Develop community ‘Whole-Antarctic’ ISSM model configuration: ACCESS-AIS3, including finalising and releasing associated end-to-end Gadi modelling workflow (pyISSM, CCD, ACCESS-ISSM). Explore and evaluate requirements to assemble idealised</p>	<p>Ice Sheet, MED, Land, Atmosphere, Ocean</p> <p><i>Collaborators: Monash, UTas, AAD/AAPP</i></p>	2.6

	<p>ACCESS-AIS3-AM3 and ACCESS-AIS3-OM3 components for prototype coupled model configurations.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Introduce pyISSM model analysis module powered by ESMValCore and extend visualisation capability to 3D.</i> • <i>Build ISMIP7 community ACCESS-AIS3 model configuration</i> • <i>Integrate and interface with AAD Digital East Antarctic (IDEA) program (CCD)</i> • <i>Extend CCD to include ACCESS-AIS3 configurations and model outputs</i> 		
ACCESS atmosphere model	<p>Full release of ACCESS-AM3 configurations for N96 and N512 resolutions, including implementation of automated testing. Beta release of ACCESS-AM3-chem configuration at N96.</p>	<p>Land, Atmosphere</p> <p><i>Collaborators: 21st Century Weather, CSIRO, UTas</i></p>	0.9
ACCESS land model	<p>Improve CABLE along three axes. Technical improvements will include a redesigned output layer, a full release of a pre-processor for meteorological forcings for ERA5, AGCD and ANU-Climate datasets and extended automated tests. Scientific improvements will focus on progressing the merging of the science between the CABLE-POP_TRENDY branch and the main branch. Finally, we will implement a full release workflow for supported configurations with full provenanced inputs, including a configuration to run CABLE offline in an ACCESS context.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Reorganisation of CABLE namelist</i> • <i>Unify CABLE core code across offline and ESM3 applications</i> • <i>Release of a CABLE configuration with an urban scheme</i> 	<p>Land</p> <p><i>Collaborators: CSIRO</i></p>	1.8
ACCESS regional atmosphere model	<p>Beta release of ACCESS-rAM3-CABLE, including the rAM3 Spack build, upgrading to UM13.8 and specification of the initial conditions. Development of a model description paper. Alpha release of ACCESS-rAM3 with support for initial and boundary conditions from a global climate model. Improve netcdf conversion and data standardisation.</p>	<p>Land, Atmosphere</p> <p><i>Collaborators: 21st Century Weather, CSIRO, UTas</i></p>	0.85

	<p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for rAM3 driven by global rerun from startdump • Incorporation of ACCESS-NRI developments of ACCESS-rAM3 into the UKMO RAS/RNS repository. • Support chemistry community adopting rAM3 with GLOMAP/CASIM • Familiarity and tracking LFRic development in preparation for rAM4-LFRic 		
ACCESS ocean/sea-ice model	<p>Alpha release of ACCESS-OM3 8km. Release ACCESS-OM3 with WOMBATmid (beta). Alpha release of 100km ACCESS-OM3 with WW3. Work with community to continue feature testing and evaluation of ACCESS-OM3.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with community to write an evaluation paper of the ACCESS-OM3 configurations • Support community-contributed idealised mom6 configs • Offline tracer capability in ACCESS-OM3 	<p>Ocean</p> <p><i>Collaborators:</i> COSIMA</p>	2.25
ACCESS regional coupled model	<p>Support the 21st Century Weather development of a new ACCESS-rCM3 by providing a common Spack-based deployment with ACCESS-CM3 and aligning with ACCESS-NRI infrastructure. This includes support for merging changes to the CM3 source code to create a single, ACCESS-NRI supported executable for regional and global coupled models.</p>	<p>Regional and Coastal Ocean, Atmosphere</p> <p><i>Collaborators:</i> 21st Century Weather</p>	0.15
ACCESS regional ocean model	<p>Expand range of ACCESS-ROM3 (regional ocean model) applications. This includes an alpha release of a PanAntarctic model with and without ice shelves, and a “generic” configuration for interfacing with regional mom6 toolbox</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of multiple “generic” configuration files such as for running ERA5 forcing and setting up WOMBAT biogeochemistry. 	<p>Regional and Coastal Ocean, Ocean</p> <p><i>Collaborators:</i> 21st Century Weather</p>	0.5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modifying the regional mom6 toolbox so it can be used for creating biogeochemical initial conditions. 		
Coastal modelling commons	Continue contributing to shared scripts and models for regional and coastal ocean modelling. Work will include assisting community groups in sharing model configuration and notebooks and an alpha release of an Australia-wide configuration. This will include sharing outputs for community use.	Regional and Coastal Ocean, Model Release <i>Collaborators: UNSW</i>	0.35

* ACCESS-NRI team information: <https://www.access-nri.org.au/teams/all-access-nri-teams/>

**Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity. Stretch goals are not included in the total FTE.

Infrastructure

ACCESS-NRI’s infrastructure activities support the reliable release and operation of the ACCESS model suite. In FY2026–27, we will enhance the systems that underpin continuous integration, model building and deployment and our telemetry systems (Table 2). Key priorities include work towards better portability of ACCESS to other HPC platforms, improved developer experience and expanding configuration testing to Rose/Cylc workflows. We will continue to manage the ACCESS-NRI merit allocation at NCI and expand our monitoring framework to track the uptake and impact of models, data and tools.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 7

Table 2: Infrastructure activities for FY2026–27

Activity	Description	Team(s)*	Effort**
Model build infrastructure	Maintain and support Spack model build infrastructure. Upgrade and unify builds of models using UKMO software to only use GitHub-based sources where required. Maintain and upgrade the UKMO partnership licensing portal and infrastructure, including adding workflows for the review of users.	Model Release, Software Transformation, Atmosphere, Land	1.3
Model configuration run tools	Support and develop payu for running models, including deployment infrastructure and post-processing tools. Improve user experience. Add support for other HPC platforms (queue software). Add support for GPU workloads. Investigate wider adoption for other ACCESS models and non-HPC (CABLE). Support rose+cylc workflows	Model Release, Atmosphere, Land, Ocean, Software Transformation, User Training	1.6

	<p>and upgrade to cylc8, including updating the documentation and training.</p> <p><i>Stretch:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Add support for other platforms and use cases</i> 		
Model configuration testing	<p>Maintain, upgrade and support model configuration CI. Add performance testing.</p> <p><i>Stretch:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Investigate improvements to the one-configuration-per-branch paradigm</i> 	Model Release, Software Transformation	0.35
Model release CI/CD	<p>Maintain and support CI/CD pipeline for model release. Add in support for generic model component CI testing.</p> <p><i>Stretch:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Investigate PBS based model builds</i> 	Model Release, Atmosphere, Land, Ocean, Ice Sheet, Regional and Coastal Ocean	1.0
Monitoring and impact tracking	<p>Maintain and support reporting and provenance infrastructure across ACCESS-NRI, including experiment telemetry, model release database, GitHub, Zenodo and NCI resource tracking. This includes developing automated reporting tools, porting NCI resource monitoring to Django, extending telemetry to Rose/Cylc and strengthening usage tracking across MED tools.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Experiment database user portal (prototype)</i> • <i>Support additional telemetry targets</i> • <i>Extended telemetry for MED tools</i> 	Model Release, MED, User Training, Atmosphere, Land, Ocean, Regional and Coastal Ocean, Ice Sheet	1.2
Preparing for new platforms	<p>Deploy payu and ACCESS-OM3 on setonix (Pawsey) to increase access to compute resources. Investigate requirements for new HPC infrastructure at NCI.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Setonix GPU Support (Cray compilers)</i> • <i>Deploy ACCESS-OM2 and ACCESS-ESM1.6 on setonix</i> • <i>Release of benchcab and meorg_client with full portability to other systems and some other land models</i> 	Model Release, Ocean, Land, Regional and Coastal Ocean, Software Transformation	0.6
ACCESS-NRI merit allocation	<p>Management of the ACCESS-NRI merit allocation for access to NCI compute and storage resources. These resources are provided to support community members to undertake</p>	Cross-organisation	0.25

	scientific simulations using ACCESS models and share community reference datasets.		
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Software and data

Software and data activities for FY2026-27 focus on strengthening the tools, standards and workflows that support ACCESS-related datasets and model outputs (Table 3). Priorities this year include continued development of tools for CMIP7-related activities, improving data standardisation and quality control, expanding data discovery capabilities and supporting reproducible evaluation and analysis workflows. The plan also includes ongoing work to improve software usability, support emerging AI/ML applications and continued support for ACCESS scaling and optimisation.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6

Table 3: Software and data activities for FY2026–27

Activity	Description	Team(s)*	Effort**
Data releases and data management	<p>Data management of ACCESS model outputs and related datasets. Activities include supporting data sharing through the ACCESS Community Datapools (including the Cryosphere Community Datapool) and NCI Data Collections, managing data requests, and supporting the publication of control experiments associated with model releases over the year.</p> <p><i>Stretch goals:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Published input datasets for CABLE configurations</i> • <i>Publication of control experiments for ACCESS-AM3 released configurations</i> • <i>Publication of control experiments for ACCESS-OM3 released configurations</i> • <i>Add ISMIP6 data support</i> 	<p>Data, Ice Sheet</p> <p><i>Collaborators: NCI, Monash, UTas, Community Working Groups</i></p>	0.55
ACCESS-NRI Conda environments	<p>Provide ongoing support for community Conda environments hosted on project xp65 at NCI, including the analysis3 environment. This includes regular maintenance and updates to scientific packages, responding to user requests for additional packages, and managing the full lifecycle of environments. It also includes exploring and implementing solutions to improve overall user experience,</p>	MED	0.2

	including environment usability, performance and accessibility.		
Data discovery	Develop and maintain a unified data discovery capability across ACCESS-NRI data holdings, spanning the ACCESS Community Datapools and data published through NCI Collections. This includes continued support and maintenance of the Python-based ACCESS-NRI Intake catalogue and delivery of a new web-based data viewer as a central discovery interface for all ACCESS-related data. Additional work includes enhancing search capabilities (including CMIP-aware search) and enabling integration with downstream workflows such as CMORisation (e.g. MOPPy) and analysis tools (e.g. ESMValCore, intake-esgf).	MED, Data <i>Collaborators:</i> NCI	0.3
Data standardisation and quality control	Progress ACCESS-MOPPy enhancements for CMIP7 Fast Track and continue development of ACCESS data specifications to improve the consistency, standardisation and usability of ACCESS model outputs. Priority specifications include AM3, OM3, CM3 and rAM3 (with CABLE). Implement quality control, validation and publishing workflows aligned with international standards, including ESGF checks, CF checkers and CI-based conformance testing.	MED, Data, Model Release Land, Atmosphere, Ocean	1.05
Data visualisation	Create high-impact visualisations to communicate ACCESS models, data outputs and science across the community. This includes delivering visualisation products and associated communication and outreach materials, alongside an Expression of Interest process for project selection.	MED, Business	1.0
Emerging data techniques and optimisation	<i>Stretch goal:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore and stay across emerging data techniques and approaches, including alternative storage options, data virtualisation and optimisation of chunking and compression. 	MED, Data	n/a
Model evaluation and diagnostics tools	Ongoing support to promote a standardised, reproducible framework for evaluating ACCESS model outputs (ESM1.6, CM3, ESM3). This includes the release and maintenance of key tools and workflows such as ESMValTool, ILAMB, the Rapid Evaluation Framework (REF), and ACCESS-Vis, with a focus on improving interoperability and consistency across the evaluation ecosystem. <i>Stretch goals:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate support for CSET. Install in supported environment if support is agreed on. 	MED	0.5

Model evaluation metrics	Improve and consolidate the ACCESS evaluation recipes framework by expanding ACCESS-ENSO-Recipes into a broader ACCESS-Recipes package, strengthening integration with ESMValCore, and contributing mature diagnostics upstream to ESMValTool. To support this, enhance evaluation capabilities by incorporating diagnostics from ACCESS-Community-Hub's evaluation repositories into ESMvaltool workflows. Additionally, this would also facilitate scalability to higher-resolution systems.	MED, Ocean, Atmosphere	0.7
Code quality improvements	Modernise build systems used across all model components by setting CMake standards and best-practices, auditing and improving CMake implementations across all packages, and harmonise all model deployment infrastructure to use CMake. Improve and extend compiler support, including fixing compilation errors, compile-time warnings, and run-time warnings for Intel oneAPI and GCC compilers. <i>Stretch goal:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Support one extra compiler (e.g., Flang, NAG)</i> 	Software Transformation Model Release,	0.25
Machine learning	Continue supporting the development and maintenance of PyEarthTools, including improvements to code documentation and expanded unit test coverage. Run an Expression of Interest (EOI) process for Machine Learning projects, with selected projects receiving extended ACCESS-NRI support and preference given to collaborations across working groups. Conduct a user survey on AI/ML usage across the ACCESS community, using the results to inform strategies that improve adoption of AI/ML approaches and strengthen collaboration between the ML Working Group and other working groups.	Software Transformation <i>Collaborators: BOM</i>	0.5
Optimisation	Optimise the ACCESS-OM3 global 25km and 8km configurations. The target is for those configurations to run at a similar speed than the corresponding ACCESS-OM2 configurations. This work will also involve profiling other models, namely ACCESS-AM3, ACCESS-rAM3 and ACCESS-CM3. <i>Stretch goals:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>ACCESS-OM3 global configurations run faster than the ACCESS-OM2 ones</i> • <i>Optimisation of ACCESS-AM3</i> • <i>Optimisation of the PanAntarctic configuration</i> 	Software Transformation, Ocean	0.6
Porting ACCESS models to GPUs	Continue porting MOM6 to GPUs: port diagnostics and remaining physics needed for ACCESS-OM3, and update	Software Transformation	0.4

	<p>FMS to support GPU-to-GPU direct MPI communication. Develop variants of the ACCESS-OM3 global 8km and 25km configurations enabled to run on GPUs. Investigate next steps to port ACCESS models to GPUs and consider which model components to address next.</p> <p><i>Stretch goal:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Port MOM6 open boundaries code needed for regional modelling. • Contribute to the porting of another component (e.g., CICE6, LFRic) 	<i>Collaborators:</i> NCI, GFDL	
Public scaling guidance	Documentation and tools to provide public scaling guidance for the ACCESS models. Update existing documentation as needed and add scaling information for more models.	Software Transformation	0.1
AI coding for climate	Design and implement a policy for responsible use of AI agents for software development within ACCESS-NRI and for the packages we develop and maintain. <p><i>Stretch goal:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide training to community 	Cross-organisation	0.1

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Training and engagement

Training and engagement activities for FY2026-27 focus on strengthening the connection between ACCESS-NRI, the ACCESS community and broader Australian sectors that rely on underlying climate modelling capabilities (Table 4). Priorities this year include supporting uptake of new ACCESS releases, improving the usability and accessibility of ACCESS documentation and tools, expanding opportunities for community feedback and user experience input, and delivering targeted training aligned with community priorities and upcoming model and software releases.

The plan also includes continued support for community workshops, Community Working Groups, communication and outreach activities and user support. The ACCESS-NRI PhD Internship Program will continue to grow in FY2026-27, expanding participation to students from all ACCESS-NRI university partners following the initial launch and trial phases. In parallel, ACCESS-NRI will begin development of an updated Strategic Plan in consultation with staff, the Scientific Advisory Committee, the ACCESS-NRI Board and broader community to help guide future priorities and capability development.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 4, 5, 6 and 7

Table 4: Training and engagement activities for FY2026–27

Activity	Description	Team(s)*	Effort**
ACCESS Community Workshops	<p>Host and support the three ACCESS Community Workshops scheduled between August and November 2026 in Melbourne and Hobart. Each workshop will focus on at least 2 Community Working Groups including:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Machine Learning Workshop with Atmos and other working groups 2. ESM/Land Workshop 3. COSIMA/Cryosphere Workshop <p>Work will also include planning and preparations for the 2027 ACCESS Workshop that will be held in the following financial year.</p>	Business	1.4
Communication	<p>Communicating the impact and importance of ACCESS-NRI's software infrastructure and expertise for climate science researchers and decision-makers. This work includes ACCESS-NRI's regular newsletter (ACCESSstory), online communication channels (social media and website). Produce public releases and impact stories for each of the ACCESS releases (models, data or tools).</p>	Business	0.8
Community engagement and outreach	<p>Engagement activities that support the two-way interactions between ACCESS-NRI and our users, partners, funders and other NCRIS organisations. This work includes our annual Highlights Report, user case stories, and briefings to government. It also covers participation at outreach events (AMOS, eResearch, NYSF, National Science Week) and collaborative communication projects as part of the NCRIS Comms network and Research Infrastructure Connected (RIC).</p>	Business	0.8
ACCESS-NRI Strategic Plan	<p>Update ACCESS-NRI's Strategic Plan in partnership with the ACCESS community. This includes development of an initial draft by the Executive, followed by staged consultation with staff, the Scientific Advisory Committee, Board, and the broader ACCESS community to ensure the plan reflects community needs and priorities. The goal is to have a revised version ready for release in the following financial year.</p>	Executive, Scientific Advisory Committee, Cross-org	0.1
Governance	<p>Leadership and governance are provided by the ACCESS-NRI Board and Scientific Advisory Committee, supported by ACCESS-NRI Executive. The Business Team provides day-to-</p>	Executive, Business	1

	day administrative governance throughs finance, reporting, recruitment, staff satisfaction survey, DEI-related activities and the organisation of the staff retreat.		
ACCESS documentation	Enable effective use of ACCESS through high-quality, user-focused documentation on the ACCESS-Hive Docs platform. This includes continuous maintenance supported by ongoing updates, issue resolution, and adding new content. This also includes a review of the broader documentation ecosystem combined with user experience feedback to inform improvements, infrastructure upgrades (e.g. Read the Docs), and enhancements to structure, navigation, and usability.	User Training, Atmosphere, MED, Cross-org	0.65
ACCESS-NRI PhD internship program	Run an internship program to support 3-4 interns, with ongoing review and improvement of documentation and procedures after each round. <i>Stretch goal:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore alternative internship models and partnerships. 	User Training	0.05
ACCESS user training	Support coordination of ACCESS-related training at in-person and online events including ACCESS community workshops, AMOS 2027, and others to support ACCESS-NRI releases/tools/models or community requests. Priority training topics include model evaluation tools (MOPPy, ESMValTool, REF) and supporting users to develop evaluation metrics for their science, working with ACCESS-related data, supporting community priorities (e.g., decoding MOM6), and content aligned with upcoming model releases (e.g., ACCESS-ESM1.6, ACCESS-AIS3/pyISSM, ACCESS-ROM3). Formats may include synchronous training sessions and written/video tutorials.	User Training, Cross-org	0.9
User experience	Assess user experience across ACCESS-NRI releases and resources, with priority focus on Payu, ACCESS documentation, and data-related tools. This includes designing and delivering a user survey in the first half of FY2026-27 and gathering feedback through user experience sessions at events. Insights from this work will inform a plan to improve the usability of ACCESS-NRI tools and materials, with prioritised improvements implemented over the year.	User Training, Cross-org	0.5
User support	Triage and respond to incoming help requests via the ACCESS-Hive Forum. Conduct regular reviews of the user support scheme, which may include gathering usage metrics and community feedback.	User Training, Cross-org	0.3

ACCESS-Hive Forum	Continued maintenance and support of the ACCESS-Hive Forum as a community communication channel. <i>Stretch goal:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review and recommend ways to improve user engagement on the Forum 	Cross-org	0.1
Community Working Groups support	Support for the six ACCESS Community Working Groups. This includes facilitating the two-way flow of information between each Working Group and ACCESS-NRI developers.	ACCESS-NRI Working Group Liaisons	0.8

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Glossary

Please visit our main website for a compilation of common terms and acronyms used within this document and by the ACCESS community: <https://www.access-nri.org.au/community/access-glossary/>

Acknowledgements

The ACCESS-NRI Annual Workplans are inspired and influenced by [Atlas of Living Australia's Annual Workplan](#):

Atlas of Living Australia (2023) Atlas of Living Australia Annual Workplan 2023-24, Atlas of Living Australia, Publication Series No. 7, Canberra, Australia, pp. 19.

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